

Mentorship, Academic and Prospective Career Success in Pre-Tertiary Educational Institutions: The Ghanaian Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mentoring is a tool for developing the focus and willingness of an individual to make positive improvements. It is however to the disadvantage of the Ghanaian society to have little empirical evidence of how mentoring programs can be used as early intervention measures in complementing the education received by Ghanaian basic school students.

Method: Review of available literature on the adoption of mentoring in improving academics and career aspirations, was done through Google Scholar, ScienceDirect and JSTOR; using the keywords provided below.

Results: Mentoring can be used to enhance the Ghanaian basic school students' academic performance and career choices, as they transition from adolescence into adulthood. It can serve as a basis for which educationists can tailor and incorporate mentoring into the curriculum of basic schools in Ghana, as this would provide a sure start in accelerating the academic, personal and leadership development of the adolescent.

Conclusion: A shift towards mentoring in addressing the challenges facing Ghanaian adolescents, other than the usage of the traditional Guidance and Counselling technique, is much needed; in order that, much more opportunities for improvement and empowerment to greater achievements, are made available to students, right from the start of their academic journey.

Keyword: *Mentoring, Academic achievement, Career, Adolescent, Guidance & Counseling*

Introduction

The importance of mentoring has been demonstrated in career decision making (Amundson, Borgen, Iaquina, Butterfield, & Koert, 2010), college education (Bettinger & Baker, 2011), leader efficacy (Lester et al., 2011); as well as in various educational contexts such as in pre-service teacher education (Ambrosetti & Dekkers, 2010), mentoring in graduate schools (Busch, 1985), peer-mentoring in higher education (Colvin & Ashman, 2010), mentoring community college students (Crisp, 2010), nursing education (Huybrecht et al., 2011), and in school-based mentoring (Núñez et al., 2013). Common among these is the view that mentoring is a tool for developing the focus and willingness of an individual to make positive improvements, which informs their capacity to make pertinent life-long decisions, be it in their academics, career or in any other area.

It is however to the disadvantage of the Ghanaian society to have little empirical evidence of how mentoring can be applied to the lives of adolescent Ghanaian basic school students and more so is the Ghanaian society's oblivion to the undeniable importance and positive impact mentoring can have on the overall development of these adolescents. The subsequent review of literature will therefore be done in light of the effect mentoring relationships have at the basic school level, how mentoring addresses the issues of underachievement and academic success; as well as its influence on an adolescent's career choice.

The Concept of Mentoring

Haggard, Dougherty, Turban, and Wilbanks (2011) describe mentoring as a reciprocal relationship which grows over a period of time through regular or consistent interaction between the mentor and protégé, thereby producing developmental benefits to the protégé, (Eby, Rhodes, & Allen, 2007; Miller, Thomson, & Roush, 1989; Jean E Rhodes & DuBois, 2008; Robinson & Niemer, 2010) mainly through the improvement of their human relations as well as their leadership skills. Mentoring is further deemed to

be an important compliment to the parents' and schools' efforts in shaping a child's future by enhancing the intellectual, emotional and futuristic professional skills of the mentee (Crisp, 2010; Eby, Allen, Evans, Ng, & DuBois, 2008; Ginevra et al., 2015; Griffin & Galassi, 2010; Liang et al., 2008).

The form mentoring takes, be it formally structured or natural, has great influence on the level of development the adolescent protégé is likely to gain from the mentoring relationship. Sottie et al. (2013) are of the opinion that mentoring will have to take the form of a well, formally structured program, where relations between the mentor and protégé are closely monitored and assessed based on certain predetermined benchmarks, in order to be effective; all the while acknowledging that, though the formally structured mentoring relationship will give more clarity on the goals of the engagement, there is the need for mentors to engage their protégés at a more natural and personal level during the early years (Liang et al., 2008), of a protégé's education.

In support of Haggard et al. (2011)'s definition of mentoring, Liang et al. (2008) suggests that, whichever form mentoring relationships may take, opportunities should be created to utilize both natural and formally structured mentoring in order to ensure a long-term fruitful bond between the mentor and protégé (Gordon, Iwamoto, Ward, Potts, & Boyd, 2009).

Mentoring at the Basic School in Ghana

For the purposes of this study, the basic school level is defined according to the characterization made by the 2008 Education Act (Act 778) of Ghana as; two years of kindergarten, six years of primary school (upper and lower primary - three years each) and three years of junior high school.

The basic school serves as an environment where the ideologies of a student concerning how to learn, what to and what not to learn, how to relate what has been learnt to what actually happens in the society and dreams of what to be in future, starts. It also is the place where the foundation of academic and peer-social support network is built, to facilitate the intellectual and personal development of any child of school going age.

Howbeit, the weight of the curriculum and task of the teacher in making sure the curriculum is well covered most often inhibits the teachers from ensuring that the basic school students become more than just 'classroom learners' (Lampléy & Johnson, 2010), thereby severely restricting what the student is capable of achieving (Sottie et al., 2013). Hence basic school students are more often than not, unable to relate most of what has been learnt in class to how those can actually be used in their daily lives. Though there exists little to no literature on how basic school students are able to compound and apply previous knowledge on future career paths or life in general, studies at the undergraduate and post-graduate levels have shown that the gap students face in transferring what has been studied in class, to what the industry needs when they start their careers (Harvey, 2000) is greatly increased, thereby making them somewhat aloof concerning their path of professional development.

It is therefore imperative that mentoring programs are used as early intervention measures in complementing the education received by Ghanaian basic school students, as this would provide a sure start in accelerating the academic, personal and leadership development of the adolescent (King et al., 2002; Lester et al., 2011; Núñez et al., 2013).

Mentoring, underachievement and academic success.

Underachievement is said to be one's failure to reach his or her full potential, in terms of academic goals or in accordance with Gallagher (2005)'s definition, "the discrepancy between a child's current academic performance and innate ability to improve". As such, several studies (Dotterer & Lowe, 2011; Liang et al., 2008) have been conducted, to accentuate the need for mentors and an effective student-teacher relationship, in ensuring an early adolescent's ability to strive for academic success.

Conversely, the study conducted by Abukari and Laser (2013) opined that, the effect of mentoring on Ghanaian students' academic grades, significantly rode on the gender of the student. They found the

effect of mentoring to be negative with regards to female students and further attributed the cause of their results, to the Ghanaian cultural context, which does not encourage a congenial teaching and learning relationship between the teacher and the pupil. In spite of this finding, McClelland, Yewchuk, and Mulcahy (1993) and Patrick, Ryan, and Kaplan (2007) emphasize on the prevalence of emotional, academic and peer support from both teachers and students within an educational context, so as to foster student engagement within the classroom.

Similarly, Patrick et al. (2007) suggest that, a school whose environment encourages self-study (Kim, 2008), celebrates students' efforts and successes, creates a continued interactive atmosphere between and amongst those who are part of it (Riley & Macbeath, 2003) as well as uplifts the self-esteem of its students (King et al., 2002) by encouraging them to view their mistakes as nothing more than a stepping stone in the learning curve; will most likely have their students being engaged with the school, inspired and exhibiting much better academic achievements.

Consequently, in order to create a conducive school environment which facilitates an early intervention in ensuring the academic improvement of adolescents at the basic school level in Ghana; the role of parents cannot be undermined (Griffin & Galassi, 2010; Jean E. Rhodes, Grossman, & Resch, 2000; Wang & Holcombe, 2010; Yirci & Kocabas, 2010), irrespective of the seemingly few hours their wards spend in their company within a day.

In this vein, Sottie et al. (2013) posit the need for schools and parents to work collaboratively. Prior to this assertion, the authors in 2011 revealed that the traditional attitude and involvement of Ghanaian parents toward their wards' education within the public basic schools was virtually non-existent. However, the focus in deducing this finding was more within the public basic schools rather than private ones, leading to the inability of this finding to be generalized; a gap which this study seeks to bridge as well.

As evidence from the study of Yirci and Kocabas (2010) suggests, parents within a school can have tremendous influence on the type of education their wards are to have, creating an avenue for these parents to contribute their expertise, experiences and resources in ensuring that the school and their wards for that matter, do not suffer any form of underachievement be it academic or otherwise.

Mentoring effect on protégé's career

As adolescents progress through their developmental stages, their thinking with regards to their career choices and opportunities also goes through the growth mill (Howard & Walsh, 2010); suggesting that, early interventions such as mentoring, may serve to propel their career aspirations towards the right path (Lester et al., 2011; Liang et al., 2008). However, there is very little literature that addresses the need for career mentoring for adolescents as they emerge into adulthood.

Subsequently, though the authors did not take into consideration how the specific relationship between mentors and adolescents may account for the future career choices of the adolescent, Howard and Walsh (2010) opine that the adolescent is constantly influenced by the gendered roles and occupations (Schuetz et al., 2012) of the adults present in his or her life.

Howard and Walsh (2010) further state that through these frequent associations and interests developed over time, the adolescent is capable of understanding the kind of training that is needed in pursuing one occupation or another.

Moreover, studies as that of Liang et al. (2008), clearly show that the word mentor may apply to both or either familial or non-familial adults in an adolescent's life, playing the specified role, as stipulated by Haggard et al. (2011). Hence, everyday interaction with familial adults is a prevalent characteristic in the adolescent's life (Abukari & Laser, 2013; Liang et al., 2008), as they maneuver their emotional, psychological and physical challenges.

Nonetheless, the Ghanaian society is riddled with such familial adults who are either too busy trying to provide financially for the family or uninvolved in their ward's education, as shown in the studies conducted by both Abukari and Laser (2013) and Sottie et al. (2013). This significantly influences the

adolescent's thought process as to the level of care, attention and involvement (Gordon et al., 2009; McClelland et al., 1993; Patrick et al., 2007) he or she is able to derive from the familial adult. Ginevra et al. (2015) suggests the need for familial adults to encourage career exploration with their charges, while instilling in them, a sense of support for what the future world of work may hold.

Conclusion

As Liang et al. (2008) puts it, a shift towards mentoring in addressing the challenges facing Ghanaian adolescents, other than the usage of the traditional Guidance and Counselling technique, is much needed; in order that, much more opportunities for improvement and empowerment to greater achievements, are made available to students, right from the start of their academic journey.

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